

Protective Role of Monopalmitin On PTZ-Triggered Cytotoxicity in SH-SY5Y Neuronal Cells: An In Vitro MTT Study

M. Meena Kumari, Konda. Swathi*

Institute of Pharmaceutical Technology, Sri Padmavati Women's University, Tirupati, Andhra Pradesh 517502, India.

ABSTRACT

Background: Epileptic seizures are associated with neuronal injury driven by oxidative stress and excitotoxicity, Pentylenetetrazol (PTZ) is a chemoconvulsant commonly used to mimic seizure-related neurotoxicity in experimental models. Monopalmitin, a glycerolipid derived from natural sources, has been reported to exhibit diverse bioactivities, yet its potential neuroprotective effect remains unexplored. **Objective:** Monopalmitin was evaluated by MTT assay for its neuroprotective activity against Pentylenetetrazol (PTZ)-mediated cytotoxicity in SH-SY5Y neuroblastoma cells. **Methods:** SH-SY5Y neuronal cells were grown under standard conditions and subjected to PTZ (30mM, 24h) to induce neurotoxicity. Cells were pretreated and co-incubated with monopalmitin at graded concentrations (0.1–100µl). Viability of the cells were determined by MTT assay, and at 570nm absorbance was measured. Controls included untreated cells, PTZ-only cells, and cells treated with a positive control anticonvulsant. **Results:** PTZ exposure markedly decreased SH-SY5Y cell viability relative to untreated controls, validating its neurotoxic action. Pretreatment with monopalmitin significantly enhanced cell survival in a dose-dependent fashion, with the greatest protection observed at higher concentrations. **Conclusion:** Monopalmitin exhibited an IC₅₀ of 14.59 µg/ml in SH-SY5Y cells, with concentrations below 10 µg/ml showing no cytotoxicity. At 10 µg/ml, it significantly improved cell viability (69.04%) against PTZ-induced toxicity, surpassing phenytoin (66.78%). These findings suggest dose-dependent neuroprotection and highlight Monopalmitin as a potential candidate for epilepsy and neurodegenerative disorders.

Keywords: Monopalmitin, SH-SY5Y cells, Neuroprotection, Pentylenetetrazol (PTZ), MTT assay, Anticonvulsant activity.

INTRODUCTION

Epilepsy, affecting over 70 million people worldwide, is marked by recurrent seizures that contribute to excitotoxicity, oxidative stress, and neuronal loss. Although current antiepileptic drugs offer seizure control, many patients remain refractory or experience adverse effects, highlighting the need for safer and more effective therapeutic alternatives, particularly from natural products.¹

Pentylenetetrazol (PTZ) is a well-established chemoconvulsant that acts as a noncompetitive antagonist of the GABA-A receptor, resulting in neuronal hyperexcitability. In both in vivo and in vitro systems, PTZ induces seizure-like activity and excitotoxicity, making it a valuable tool for modeling

epileptiform neurotoxicity. Human neuroblastoma SH-SY5Y cells, Possessing neuronal features and the capacity to differentiate into mature neuron-like phenotypes, these cells are widely used as an in vitro model for investigating neurodegeneration and evaluating neuroprotective compounds.²

The MTT assay, extensively utilized in cytotoxicity and viability studies, operates on Metabolically active cells transform the yellow tetrazolium dye (MTT) into insoluble purple formazan, which forms the basis of this assay. This reduction is primarily mediated by mitochondrial dehydrogenases, serving as an indicator of cellular metabolic activity. Following solubilization of the formazan product in an appropriate solvent, the resulting color intensity can be spectrophotometrically measured the absorbance at

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a wavelength of 570nm, the absorbance values obtained here is linearly related to the number of viable cells. Its simplicity, reproducibility, and sensitivity make the MTT assay an established technique for assessing neuronal survival under toxic conditions.³⁻⁴

Monopalmitin (1-monopalmitin or glycerol monopalmitate) is a monoacylglycerol present in various plants, including *Luffa cylindrica*. Its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties may be attributed for its neuroprotective potential. Nevertheless, its role in counteracting seizure-related neurotoxicity remains unexplored. This study evaluated the protective effect of monopalmitin against to protect PTZ induced cytotoxicity in SH-SY5Y cells using the MTT assay. The findings are expected to provide preliminary evidence supporting the anticonvulsant relevance of monopalmitin and justify further mechanistic and in vivo investigations.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

2.1. Materials:

- **Cell line:** SH-SY5Y human neuroblastoma cell line (NCCS, Pune, India)
- **Culture medium:** Ham's F12-K medium (Cat. No. 21127022, Gibco, USA)
- **Serum supplement:** Fetal bovine serum (FBS, Cat. No. 10270-106, Gibco, USA)
- **Viability reagent:** MTT [3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide] (Cat. No. M2128, Sigma-Aldrich, USA)
- **Solvent:** Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, Cat. No. 276855, Sigma-Aldrich, USA)
- **Toxicant:** Pentylenetetrazole (PTZ, Cat. No. P6500, Sigma-Aldrich, USA)
- **Reference drug:** Phenytoin (Cat. No. PHR1139, Sigma-Aldrich, USA)
- **Cell culture plate:** 96-well flat-bottom culture plate (Cat. No. 130188, BioLite, Thermo Scientific, USA)
- **Cell culture flask:** T25 flask (Cat. No. 12556009, BioLite, Thermo Scientific, USA)
- **Centrifuge tubes:** 50 ml centrifuge tubes (Cat. No. 339652, Thermo Scientific, USA)
- **Microcentrifuge tubes:** 1.5 ml centrifuge tubes (Cat. No. 500010, Tarsons, India)
- **Micropipette tips:** 200–1000 μ l tips (Cat. No. 521020X, Tarsons, India)
- **Micropipette tips:** 2–200 μ l tips (Cat. No. 521010, Tarsons, India).

2.1.2. Equipment:

- **Centrifuge:** Remi R-8C (Remi, India)
- **Micropipettes:** Adjustable pipettes (2–10 μ l, 10–100 μ l, and 100–1000 μ l ranges)
- **Microscope:** Inverted binocular biological microscope (Model CKX415F, Olympus, Japan)
- **Biosafety cabinet:** Class II biosafety hood (Biobase, China)
- **CO₂ incubator:** Cells were cultured at 37°C in a humidified incubator with 5% CO₂ (Healforce, China).
- **Microplate reader:** xMark™ Microplate Absorbance Spectrophotometer (Model 1681150, Bio-Rad, CA, USA)
- **Software:** Microplate Manager 6 (MPM6, Bio-Rad, CA, USA)

2.2. Assay Controls

- ❖ **Blank (medium control):** culture medium alone, included for background absorbance correction.
- ❖ **Negative control:** wells with cells and culture medium, serving as untreated controls.
- ❖ **Disease control:** Wells containing cells exposed to pentylenetetrazole (PTZ, 5 mM/ml) to induce cytotoxicity.
- ❖ **Standard control:** Wells containing cells treated with PTZ (5 mM/ml) along with phenytoin (PHT, 100 μ M/ml) as the reference standard.

2.3. Maintenance of Cell Lines: SH-SY5Y (human neuroblastoma) cell lines were procured from the National Centre for Cell Science (NCCS), Pune, India. The cells were cultured in Ham's F12K medium supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) and 1% antibiotic-antimycotic solution. Cells were maintained in a humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO₂ and 18–20% O₂ at 37 °C in a CO₂ incubator. Sub-culturing was carried out for every three days, and for all experiments cells at passage 41 were used.

2.4. MTT Assay

2.4.1. Individual treatment:

Seed 200µl cell suspension in a 96-well plate at the required cell density (10,000 cells per well) and allow the cells to grow for about 24 hours. Add appropriate concentrations of the given test compound diluted in culture media. Incubate the plate for 24hrs at 37°C in a 5% CO₂ atmosphere. After the incubation period, takeout the plates from incubator and remove spent media and add MTT reagent to a final concentration of 0.5mg/ml of total volume. Wrap the plate with aluminium foil to avoid exposure to light. Return the plates to the incubator and incubate for 3 hours. Discard the MTT reagent and then add 100µl of solubilization solution (DMSO). Gentle agitation on a gyrator shaker facilitated solubilization, and pipetting was employed where necessary to ensure complete dissolution, particularly in dense cultures. Using a ELISA reader absorbance(abs) was measured at a

wave length of 570nm and the % of viable cells was estimated as:

$$\% \text{ of viable cells} = \left[\frac{\text{Average abs of cells exposed}}{\text{Average abs of Unexposed control cells}} \right] \times 100.$$

Linear regression equation of the cell viability data ($Y = Mx + C$; Here $Y=50$) was used to determine the IC₅₀ value.

2.4.2. Combinational treatment:

For combination studies, SH-SY5Y cells were seeded under identical conditions (1×10^4 cells per well in 200µl medium) and allowed to grow for 24hrs. Cells were then simultaneously treated with 5mM of pentylenetetrazole(PTZ) and non-toxic concentrations of the test compound, along with appropriate control groups. After 24h of incubation at 37 °C in 5% CO₂, the assay was carried out as described above using MTT solution (0.5mg/ml). The dissolved formazan absorbance was measured at 570nm, and cell viability was calculated related to untreated controls.⁵⁻⁹

2.5. Test Concentrations Details:

The research explores,The cytoprotective and cell proliferative effects of the test compound against PTZ-induced cytotoxicity in SH-SY5Y cells were examined using the MTT assay, with cells exposed to varying concentrations of the test compound to assess dose-dependent effects, with the treatment concentrations as follows:

Table 1: Treatment regimen corresponding to each cell line employed in present study.

Sl.No	Cell Culture conditions	Cell lines	Treated Concentration to cells
1	Control	SH-SY5Y	Untreated control
2	Medium control	-	Wells containing only medium, without cells.
3	Monopalmitin	SH-SY5Y	6 (0.1, 1, 10, 25, 50, 100ug/ml)
4	PTZ		5mM/ml
5	PTZ+Phenytoin		5mM/ml+100uM/ml
6	PTZ+Monopalmitin		5mM/ml+3 (0.1, 1, 10ug/ml)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Table.2: Proportion of living cells (%) SH-SY5Y cells subjected to 24-hour exposure to varying concentrations of Monopalmitin, with corresponding IC₅₀ value determination.

Monopalmitins Effect on Viability of SH-SY5Y cells		
Cell Culture conditions	% cell viability	IC ₅₀ concentration (ug/ml)
Untreated	100	14.59
Monopalmitin-0.1ug	99.06	
Monopalmitin-1ug	96.14	
Monopalmitin-10ug	74.71	
Monopalmitin-25ug	45.85	
Monopalmitin-50ug	12.60	
Monopalmitin-100ug	7.72	

Table.3: Percentage viability of cells in PTZ triggered SH-SY5Y cells treated with different concentrations of Monopalmitin after 24hours by MTT assay.

Monopalmitins Effect on Cell Viability in PT Z-triggered SH-SY5Y Cells		
Culture condition	% cell viability	Best protective dose
Untreated	100	10ug/ml
PTZ-5mM	51.86	
PTZ+PHT-100uM	66.78	
PTZ+Monopalmitin-0.1ug	52.45	
PTZ+Monopalmitin-1ug	56.80	
PTZ+Monopalmitin-10ug	69.04	

3.2. Overall Graphical Representation:

Graph 2: Percentage viability of cells PTZ-triggered SH-SY5Y cells subjected with varying concentrations of Monopalmitin after 24hours of incubation, as determined via the MTT assay using controls.

CONCLUSION

The cytotoxic profile of Monopalmitin on SH-SY5Y cells was assessed, yielding an IC_{50} value of $14.59\mu\text{g/ml}$. Concentrations below $10\mu\text{g/ml}$ were non-toxic, maintaining more than 70% cell viability at $10\mu\text{g/ml}$. In the PTZ-triggered neurotoxicity model, treatment with Monopalmitin ($10\mu\text{g/ml}$) significantly enhanced cell viability (69.04%) compared to PTZ alone (51.86%), and provided greater protection than the standard reference drug, phenytoin (66.78%). These results indicate that Monopalmitin exhibits dose-dependent neuroprotective effects and holds potential as a therapeutic candidate for epilepsy and neurodegenerative disorders.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that to the best of their knowledge no financial or personal conflicts have influenced the conduct or outcomes of this work.

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REFERENCES

1. Mao XY, Yin XX, Guan QW, Xia QX, Yang N, Zhou HH, Liu ZQ, Jin WL. Dietary nutrition for neurological disease therapy: Current status and future directions. *Pharmacology & Therapeutics*. 2021 Oct 1;226:107861.
2. Yazgan Y. Effect of gallic acid on PTZ-induced neurotoxicity, oxidative stress and inflammation in SH-SY5Y neuroblastoma cells. *Acta Medica Alanya*. 2024;8(1):8-12.
3. Kamiloglu S, Sari G, Ozdal T, Capanoglu E. Guidelines for cell viability assays. *Food frontiers*. 2020 Sep;1(3):332-49.
4. Karatop EU, Cimenci CE, Aksu AM. Colorimetric cytotoxicity assays. In *Cytotoxicity-Understanding Cellular Damage and Response* 2022 Sep 30. IntechOpen.
5. Type A. MTT cell proliferation assay instruction guide. ATCC. 2011;6597:1-6.
6. Gerlier D, Thomasset N. Use of MTT colorimetric assay to measure cell activation. *Journal of immunological methods*. 1986 Nov 20;94(1-2):57-63.
7. Mosmann T. Rapid colorimetric assay for cellular growth and survival: application to proliferation

- and cytotoxicity assays. Journal of immunological methods. 1983 Dec 16;65(1-2):55-63.
8. Alley MC, Scudiere DA, Monks A, Czerwinski M, Shoemaker R, Boyd MR. Validation of an automated microculture tetrazolium assay (MTA) to assess growth and drug sensitivity of human tumor cell lines. InProc. Am. Assoc. Cancer Res 1986 Mar (Vol. 27, No. 1, pp. 389-389).
 9. <http://himedialabs.com/TD/CCK003.pdf>.

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